

Epidemiology and Characteristics of Burn Injury Patients in Dr. M. Ashari Regional General Hospital: A 5-Year Retrospective Study

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ABSTRACT

Burn injury is one of the major global health burdens, which causes permanent changes to patients, thus influencing their quality of life, and accounts for 180,000 deaths annually in low- and middle-income countries. The aim of this research was to describe the epidemiology and characteristics of burn injury patients in Dr.M.Ashari Regional General Hospital. This research was a descriptive retrospective study, where the data was collected from burn injury patients' medical records who were hospitalized in Dr.M.Ashari Regional General Hospital during 2018-2022. Out of 96 burn injury cases, 82 cases were included. The result showed the total cases of burn injury patients were 32 in 2018, 31 in 2019, 8 in 2020, 6 in 2021, and 5 in 2022. There were 55 males (67.1%) and 27 females (32.9%), with 59 adults (72%) and 23 children (28%). Burn injury was predominantly caused by scald (45.1%), followed by electricity (35.4%), with the most frequent clinical characteristics were superficial-mid dermal degree, involving extremity, and 1-10% TBSA. The average length of stay was 4.5 days, with a 7.3% mortality rate. These results were expected to help clinicians and policymakers to further understand the epidemiology and characteristics of burn injury in Indonesia and aid in implementing effective preventive strategies.

KEYWORDS: Burn injury, epidemiology, characteristics, mortality

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
26 August 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

I. INTRODUCTION

Burn injury is still a main health issue globally.^{1,2} Burn injury causes acute changes in skin composition, which result in cell death along with protein denaturation and then will cause damage in the skin and other organic tissues.^{1,3} The main causes of burn injury are thermal traumas which can result from hot liquids (scalds), hot items (contact burns), and/or fire (flame burns). Furthermore, burn injury can also be caused through radiation, radioactivity, electrical trauma, friction and/or contact with certain chemical substances.^{1,2,4}

According to the WHO, most cases of burn injury occur in countries with middle to low income with yearly mortalities reaching 180.000 deaths and 2/3 out of those deaths occur in areas such as Africa dan Southeast Asia.¹ Besides that, burn injury also has high morbidity numbers, which directly influence length of hospital stay, causing not only permanent changes to both normal function and

appearances, but also influences on the mental health and the quality of life for patients.^{1,4,5}

According to the data gathered from a research conducted in Cipto Mangunkusumo National Hospital in Jakarta from 2013-2017, from 709 medical records with burn injury, most of the cases were suffered by men accounting to 465 cases with a 1.9:1 ratio of men to women, and mostly found around the ages of 16-35 years old, which accounted to 269 cases. The most common cause of the burn injury found on this research was gas explosion (35,7%), followed by flame (26.7%), hot liquid (16.6%), electrical trauma (11.7%), other causes, including hot items and vapor (4.9%), and the least common cause was chemicals (4.4%). In this research, the most common grade for burn injury were grades II-III (596 cases) with the largest Total Body Surface Area (TBSA) of around >40% (211 cases).⁶

Those high numbers for morbidity and mortality from burn injury makes prevention a crucial thing.^{1,2} More information regarding the epidemiology of burn injury is

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needed to support allocation of resources and prevention of burn injury.⁴ The objective of this research was to describe the epidemiology and characteristics of burn injury patients in Dr. M. Ashari Regional General Hospital in Pemalang Indonesia. The writers of this research hoped that the results of this research can contribute data to the national data, the epidemiology of burn injuries in Indonesia, and support efforts for the prevention and treatment for burn patients in Indonesia.

II. METHODS

This research design was a descriptive retrospective study using data collected from medical records of burn injury patients treated in Dr. M. Ashari Regional General Hospital from January 2018-December 2022. The medical records of patients with burn injury diagnosis who were hospitalized during January 2018-December 2022 were included in this research. Medical records with incomplete data and with patients who were outpatient from the emergency department and hospitalized for management of old burn injury wound were excluded from this research. Data taken from these medical records included the demographic data of patients (gender and age), aetiology, location, degree of burn injury, Total Body Surface Area (TBSA), length of hospitalization, and mortality. Aetiologies of burn injury were divided into hot liquids (scalds), hot items (contacts), fire (flame), gas explosions, electrical trauma, and chemical substances. Locations of burn injury were divided into face, chest, abdomen, dorsum, buttocks, genital, extremities, and combination between each location. Degrees of burn injury were divided into epidermal, superficial-mid dermal, mid-deep dermal, deep dermal, deep dermal-full thickness, and full thickness. TBSA was the percentage of the burnt area of the skin in the body, measured using the rule-of-nine, and were divided into $\leq 10\%$, 11-20%, 21-30%, 31-40%, and $>40\%$. Length of hospitalization was defined as the time period between the admission date and the discharge date period recorded in the medical records. The data was later analysed descriptively using the IBM SPSS 23 application.^{6,7,8,9,10}

The ethical clearance of this research was approved by Research Ethical Committee of Dr. M. Ashari Regional General Hospital with ethical clearance number: EC/RSUDMA/2025/001.

III. RESULTS

Out of 96 cases, the total cases of burn injury treated in Dr. M Ashari Regional General Hospital from Januari 2018-December 2022 included in this research were 82 cases, with a decrease in the number of patients annually from 2018-2022. Most of the cases were found in 2018, which surmounted to 32 people (39%), and the least number of cases found in a year was in 2022, which was 5 people (6%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Total Number of Burn Injury Cases in Dr. M. Ashari Regional General Hospital; Divided Annually during January 2018-December 2022 and Based on Gender

Based on the patient demographic data, most of the patients were male, which amounted to 55 people (67.1%), compared to female which only surmounted to 27 cases (32.9%), with a ratio of up to 2:1. Cases were mostly found on adults (>18 years old) rather than children (≤ 18 years old). There were 59 cases for burn injury on adults (72%) and only 23 cases of burn injury on children (28%), where on both age groups, male was more predominant than female. The oldest patient found in this data was a patient aged 80 years old and the youngest age found was 1 day old. The average age of burn injury cases in this research was 30 ± 20 years old, with a median of 32 years old (Table 1).

Table 1. Patient Demographic Data

Gender	Age (Years Old)		Total (%)
	≤ 18 (%)	>18 (%)	
Male (%)	12 (14,6)	43 (52,4)	55 (67,1)
Female (%)	11 (13,4)	16 (19,5)	27 (32,9)
Total (%)	23 (28)	59 (72)	82 (100)

The most common aetiology of burn injury cases found in this research was hot liquids (scalds) amounting to 37 cases (45,1%), followed by Electrical trauma equalling to 29 cases (35,4%), fire (flame burns) with an amount of 8 cases (9,8%), gas explosions with 4 cases (4,9%), chemical substances with 3 cases (3,7%), and lastly hot items (contact burns) with 1 case (1,2%). On male, burn injury cases were mostly caused by electrical trauma, with 25 cases (30,5%), meanwhile for female, most cases were caused by hot liquids with 19 cases (23,2%). Hot liquids were the most common etiology found on burn injury cases on children with 18 cases (22%), for adults, electrical trauma was the most common aetiology with 28 cases (34,1%) (Table 2).

Burn injury cases were mostly found in locations involving the extremities; with cases of burn injury involving only the extremities amounted to 49 cases (59,8%), which were most dominantly found in adult males. In this research, we also found 3 cases of burn injury (3,7%) which involved the whole-body; including the face, chest,

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abdomen, dorsum, buttocks, genitalia, and extremities; which were also dominantly found in male patients. Based on the degree of burn injury, burn injury cases with superficial-mid dermal degree were the most common degree found with 55 cases (67.1%) and were mostly dominated by adult males. Based on the TBSA, we found that most cases involved $\leq 10\%$ TBSA with 55 cases (67,1%) and were mostly dominated by adult males. The average TBSA of burn injury cases in this research was around $11,4 \pm 14\%$ with a median number of 5%, which the largest TBSA found was 65% and the smallest was 1% (Table 2).

In this research, as much as 68 cases (82,9%) of burn injury were treated for < 7 days and 14 cases (17,1%) stayed for ≥ 7 days in the hospital. The average length of hospitalization was found to be around $4,5 \pm 2,1$ days with a median of 4 days, which the longest length of hospitalization found was 12 days and the shortest was 1 day. Males and adults were found to dominate the length of hospitalization of both < 7 days (46 cases; 56,1% and 50 cases; 61% respectively) and ≥ 7 days (9 cases; 11% and 9 cases; 11% respectively). Burn injury cases with superficial-mid dermal degree were found most frequently to be treated with a length of hospitalization of ≥ 7 days, which amounted

Table 2. The Aetiology of Burn Injury Cases Based on Gender and Age

Clinical Characteristics	Gender		Age (Years Old)		Total (%)
	Male (%)	Female (%)	≤ 18 (%)	> 18 (%)	
Aetiology					
Scald	18 (22)	19 (23,2)	18 (22)	19 (23,2)	37 (45,1)
Contact	0 (0)	1 (1,2)	1 (1,2)	0 (0)	1 (1,2)
Flame	8 (9,8)	0 (0)	3 (3,7)	5 (6,1)	8 (9,8)
Gas Explosion	1 (1,2)	3 (3,7)	0 (0)	4 (4,9)	4 (4,9)
Electrical Trauma	25 (30,5)	4 (4,9)	1 (1,2)	28 (34,1)	29 (35,4)
Chemical Substance	3 (3,7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3 (3,7)	3 (3,7)
Location					
A	1 (1,2)	0 (0)	1 (1,2)	0 (0)	1 (1,2)
D	2 (2,4)	0 (0)	1 (1,2)	1 (1,2)	2 (2,4)
E	33 (40,2)	16 (19,5)	7 (8,5)	42 (51,2)	49 (59,8)
C+A	0 (0)	2 (2,4)	2 (2,4)	0 (0)	2 (2,4)
C+E	1 (1,2)	1 (1,2)	2 (2,4)	0 (0)	2 (2,4)
A+E	0 (0)	1 (1,2)	1 (1,2)	0 (0)	1 (1,2)
D+B	2 (2,4)	1 (1,2)	3 (3,7)	0 (0)	3 (3,7)
D+E	6 (7,3)	2 (2,4)	1 (1,2)	7 (8,5)	8 (9,8)
C+A+E	2 (2,4)	3 (3,7)	3 (3,7)	2 (2,4)	5 (6,1)
A+B+E	1 (1,2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1,2)	1 (1,2)
D+G+E	0 (0)	1 (1,2)	1 (1,2)	0 (0)	1 (1,2)
C+A+D+E	1 (1,2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1,2)	1 (1,2)
C+A+D+B+E	3 (3,7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3 (3,7)	3 (3,7)
F+C+A+D+B+G+E	3 (3,7)	0 (0)	1 (1,2)	2 (2,4)	3 (3,7)
Degree					
Epidermal	3 (3,7)	0 (0)	2 (2,4)	1 (1,2)	3 (3,7)
Superficial-Mid Dermal	33 (40,2)	22 (26,8)	17 (20,7)	38 (46,3)	55 (67,1)
Mid-Deep Dermal	10 (12,2)	2 (2,4)	2 (2,4)	10 (12,2)	12 (14,6)
Deep Dermal	6 (7,3)	2 (2,4)	2 (2,4)	6 (7,3)	8 (9,8)
Deep Dermal-Full Thickness	1 (1,2)	1 (1,2)	0 (0)	2 (2,4)	2 (2,4)
Full Thickness	2 (2,4)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (2,4)	2 (2,4)
TBSA (%)					
≤ 10	39 (47,6)	16 (19,5)	14 (17,1)	41 (50)	55 (67,1)
11-20	5 (6,1)	8 (9,8)	5 (6,1)	8 (9,8)	13 (15,9)
21-30	5 (6,1)	2 (2,4)	1 (1,2)	6 (7,3)	7 (8,5)
31-40	2 (2,4)	1 (1,2)	1 (1,2)	2 (2,4)	3 (3,7)
> 40	4 (4,9)	0 (0)	2 (2,4)	2 (2,4)	4 (4,9)
Total (%)	55 (67,1)	27 (32,9)	23 (28)	59 (72)	82 (100)

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to 5 cases (6,1%); followed by burn injury cases with mid-deep dermal dan deep dermal degree, which amounted to 4 cases (4,9%) for each degree. Based on their TBSA, burn injury cases with $\leq 10\%$ TBSA were the most common cases treated for ≥ 7 days, as much as 7 cases (8,5%), followed by cases with TBSA 21-30% as much as 3 cases (3,7%). Mortality number for burn injury cases in Dr. M. Ashari Regional General Hospital Pematang were only found

inadult males with 6 cases (7,3%). The burn injury degree of superficial-mid dermal, mid-deep dermal, dan deep dermal were the cases responsible for the mortality numbers in this research with 2 cases (2,4%) each. Dead case(s) of burn injury was found within each TBSA group; however, the highest number was found in burn injury with TBSA $>40\%$, with 2 cases (2,4%) (Table 3).

Table 3. The Length of Hospital Stay and Mortality of Burn Injury Cases Based on Gender, Age, Burn Injury Degree, and TBSA

Demographic Data & Clinical Characteristics	Length of Stay (Days)		Mortality		Total (%)
	<7 (%)	≥ 7 (%)	Lived Cases (%)	Dead Case (%)	
Gender					
Male	46 (56,1)	9 (11)	49 (59,8)	6 (7,3)	55 (67,1)
Female	22 (26,8)	5 (6,1)	27 (32,9)	0 (0)	27 (32,9)
Age					
≤ 18	18 (22)	5 (6,1)	23 (28)	0 (0)	23 (28)
> 18	50 (61)	9 (11)	53 (64,6)	6 (7,3)	59 (72)
Degree					
I	3 (3,7)	0 (0)	3 (3,7)	0 (0)	3 (3,7)
IIA-B	50 (61)	5 (6,1)	53 (64,6)	2 (2,4)	55 (67,1)
II-III	8 (9,8)	4 (4,9)	10 (12,2)	2 (2,4)	12 (14,6)
III	4 (4,9)	4 (4,9)	6 (7,3)	2 (2,4)	8 (9,8)
III-IV	2 (2,4)	0 (0)	2 (2,4)	0 (0)	2 (2,4)
IV	1 (1,2)	1 (1,2)	2 (2,4)	0 (0)	2 (2,4)
TBSA (%)					
1-10	48 (58,5)	7 (8,5)	54 (65,9)	1 (1,2)	55 (67,1)
11-20	11 (13,4)	2 (2,4)	12 (14,6)	1 (1,2)	13 (15,9)
21-30	4 (4,9)	3 (3,7)	6 (7,3)	1 (1,2)	7 (8,5)
31-40	3 (3,7)	0 (0)	2 (2,4)	1 (1,2)	3 (3,7)
>40	2 (2,4)	2 (2,4)	2 (2,4)	2 (2,4)	4 (4,9)
Total (%)	68 (82,9)	14 (17,1)	76 (92,7)	6 (7,3)	82 (100)

IV. DISCUSSION

In this research, 96 burn injury cases were found to be treated in DR. M. Ashari Regional General Hospital from 2018-2022, but only 82 cases were included in this research. From 2018-2022, cases of burn injury decreased annually from 33 cases in 2018 to 5 cases in 2022. That downtrend was also found on research conducted by Yang, et al in China, where they found an annual decrease of burn injury cases from year to year.⁸ Setiawan, et al, in their research, also mentioned a decrease in the number of burn injury cases in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic.⁷

Burn injury cases in this research were more frequently found in males (55 cases; 67,1%), with a ratio of male to female of 2:1, and the majority of cases were found in adults (59 cases; 72%). Those results were in line with the research conducted by Setiawan, et al, where they mentioned that burn injury cases were more frequently found in males with a ratio of male to female of 4,4:1, and were mostly found in adults (>18 years old).⁷ Along with that, Yang, et al, Mego, et al, and Wardhana, et al, also mentioned that most of their

burn injury cases were found in male.^{6,8,11} There are more men that do the house maintenances and get involved in high risk career professions than women, hence men are more at risk to get burn injury both domestically and professionally.^{1,11,12} Wang, et al, also mentioned that men are the main source of income for families in China and have more opportunities to have a career than women, hence the exposure to certain jobs with high risks are more likely towards men than women.⁹ The absence of strict and clear standard operating procedures and the lack of protective equipment in certain jobs are also the main risk factors that increase the incidence of burn injury.^{1,6,9}

Hot liquids (37 cases; 45,1%) dan electrical trauma (29 cases; 35,4%) were the two most common etiologies of burn injury found in this research. That result was similar to the research conducted by Yang, et al, who mentioned that the most common etiology of burn injury found on their research was hot liquids (60,19%).⁸ In line with researches conducted by Setiawan, et al, dan Wihastyoko, et al, most cases of burn injury in male in this research were caused by

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electrical trauma (25 cases; 30,5%), meanwhile burn injury cases in female and ≤ 18 years old group were more frequently caused by hot liquids (19 cases; 23,2% and 18 cases; 22% respectively).^{7,13} The WHO mentioned that men are more likely to get burn injury due to working circumstances related to fire, hot liquids, chemicals, and electrical trauma.¹ Electrical trauma can be caused not only by both high and low voltage electrical currents, but also lightning or thunder, which causes more severe damage towards internal tissues compared to the skin injuries that can be superficially observed.^{4,14} On women and children, burn injury is more likely caused at home, especially in the kitchens due to containers spilling hot water, fire, or even gas tank explosions.¹ Burn injury in children occurs due to certain risk factors, such as lack of parental surveillance and supervision, how unprepared certain parents are in having children, the lack of knowledge on how to properly and safely boil water, put away combustible items, and choose a safe household for children.^{1,13}

In this research, burn injury cases were most commonly found in the extremities (49 cases; 59,8%), which were in line with the research conducted by Wihastyoko, et al.¹³ Momeni, et al, mentioned that there were 43% cases of burn injury in their research which involved inferior extremities, meanwhile Sasor, et al, mentioned that 80% of their burn injury cases involved superior extremities.^{15,16} In general, hands and arms are more frequently exposed, used for protective reflex movements and handling, more likely to contact with high temperature items, chemicals, electrical currents, dan moving items (friction).¹⁶

In line with the research conducted by Setiawan, et al, burn injury cases in our research were mostly dominated by superficial-mid dermal degree burn injury (55 cases; 67,1%) and $\leq 10\%$ TBSA (55 cases; 67,1%), which both characteristics were mostly found in male (33 cases; 40,2% and 39 cases; 47,6%) and adults (38 cases; 46,3% and 41 cases; 50%).⁷ Even though children, especially teenagers, are more at risk in getting burn injury, the degree of burn injury and TBSA involved are much less because children are still under parental supervision, have safe environments, and get proper treatment on time.^{8,17} Our research supported it with our results, where >18 years old group almost dominated each burn injury degree and TBSA categories. However, children and elderly people can have an even worse and more serious burn injury due to the thinness of their skin.^{9,18,19} Yang, et al, mentioned in the results of their research that burn injury cases involving 0-10% TBSA were higher in age group of 0-10 and 10-20 year old, then the number of burn injury cases were decreasing along with the increasing of age.⁸ On the other hand, along with the increasing of age, the likeliness of burn injury cases involving larger TBSA is increasing due to certain fields of work, as well as the restricted mobility and instability of elderly, which result in longer contact with the heat source

and delayed management of the burn injury.^{8,19} Related to work, even though high-voltage electrical current causes burn injury with smaller TBSA, the degree of burn injury is usually deeper, involving the whole dermatological and subcutaneous structures (full thickness burn injury, III degree), which the prognosis is generally worse and has a high chance in acquiring disability.^{9,20}

The average length of hospitalization for burn injury in this research was $4,5 \pm 2,1$ days, ranging from 1-12 days, with a median of 4 days. Those results were similar to the research conducted by Chukamei, et al (average of 3,2 days).²¹ The length of hospital stay for burn injury depends on factors such as age, urbanity, insurance, etiology, location, degree of burn injury, TBSA, comorbidities, antibiotic usage, skin grafts, and the patient's discharge status.^{9,21} In children, since their absorbable nutrition are divided for the purposes of growth and recovery of the wound, their length of hospital stay will usually be longer than adults.⁹ Even though adults whose organ functions improve with age have a shorter length of hospital stay due to their energy being fully invested in recovery, in elderly patients, their length of hospital stay will be longer due to impaired physical function and psychosocial factors.^{9,19} Deeper burn injury grades and greater TBSA require longer time periods for skin regeneration and could cause serious exudation of more serious wound, disrupting the internal environment of the wound, hence why patients with those types of burn injury require longer hospital stay.^{9,21} That was why the length of hospital stay in our research was shorter than in the research conducted by Wardhana, et al (average 15 days; median 12, time frame 1-157 days). In our research, most of the burn injury cases found were grade superficial-mid dermal with TBSA $\leq 10\%$, meanwhile in their research, the burn injury cases were mostly grade superficial-deep dermal with TBSA $>40\%$.⁶

The number of mortalities in our research were 6 cases (7,3%), in line with results from the research conducted by Setiawan, et al (8 cases; 7,4%).⁷ Factors that influence the mortality rate of burn injury are age, degree, TBSA, and length of hospitalization.¹⁵ Mortality number for burn injury cases in this research were only found in adult males with 6 cases (7,3%). The burn injury degree of superficial-mid dermal, mid-deep dermal, dan deep dermal were the cases responsible for the mortality numbers in this research with 2 cases (2,4%) each. Dead case(s) of burn injury was found within each TBSA group; however, the highest number was found in burn injury with TBSA $>40\%$, with 2 cases (2,4%) Those results were similar with the research conducted by Wardhana, et al, which mentioned that extensive burn injury with TBSA of $>40\%$ and superficial-deep dermal degree contributed most of the death cases.⁶ Setiawan, et al, also mentioned similar results, where adults male and TBSA of 51-60% and 71-100% contributed most of the death cases of burn injury.⁷ Older individuals tend to have pre-existing

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comorbidities, which not only increase susceptibility to various complications, but also poorer in-hospital outcomes.¹⁹ Extensive burn injury often lead to immunocompromised patients, which are at increased risk for infection, sepsis and multi-system organ failure.²² Although it was not specified in this research, Wardhana, et al, mentioned various causes of deaths of burn injury cases in their research, which were septic shock (48,6%), Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) (11,5%), other causes including cardiac arrest, acute renal failure, and other complications (10,9%), multi-organ failure (9,3%), and other causes not found in medical records (19,6%).⁶ Besides those factors, different management techniques, infection control, and efficient resuscitation play a role in the fatality of burn injury.¹⁰

This research had some limitations and weaknesses. This study was done in a hospital with no burn unit. The burn injury cases in our hospital were handled by several general surgeons with their own perspective in diagnosis and management of the cases. Patients' socioeconomical data, comorbidities, treatment of choice, and cause of deaths were not available in this research, hence limiting further analysis. This research design was descriptive, hence why this research conveyed data, which were available and reachable, without finding a further correlation and/or the cause-and-effect relationship. Other than that, this research was conducted in one of the hospitals in a certain province in Indonesia, where further and deeper researches should be conducted involving more hospitals in multiple provinces in Indonesia to be able to disclose more comprehensive data.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This research described the epidemiology and characteristics of patients with burn injury in Dr. M. Ashari Regional General Hospital in Pemalang from Januari 2018 - December 2022. There were 82 cases of burn injury included in this research, where there were constant annual decreases in the number of burn injury cases. Patients with burn injury in this research were predominantly male and adults. In general, the most common etiology of burn injury in this research were hot liquids, which were also the most common causes for burn injury in female and ≤ 18 years old group, while electrical trauma was the most common cause in male and adults. The characteristics of burn injury that were most commonly found in this research were grade IIA-B, involved the extremities, 1-10% TBSA, and had an average length of hospital stay of $4,5 \pm 2,1$ days, with a mortality number of 6 cases (7,3%). These results were expected to help clinicians and policymakers to further understand the epidemiology and characteristics of burn injury in Indonesia and aid in implementing effective preventive strategies.

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